

Oliver Drerup
Thornton, P.O. Campton
New Hampshire. 03223.

14th January, 1969.

Dear Andrew:

Visions of you working yourself to the bone, twelve places at once with the need and desire to be in thirteen.

David Whitehouse informs me that you are doing a DPhil at Oxford based on the Institute, also that your interest is in the trade routes of Southern Iran. As fate would have it I am involved in my thesis work with a study of Caliphate Fars. It would be no end of help to me if we might discuss by mail (in view of my inability to be in Iran this season) the sorts of problems you are encountering. In what aspects does survey prove most difficult on the ground? What is needed to adjust to the terrain? What in Fars do you hope to cover? What is your procedure? Would you consider my assistance in the field as an apprentice?

Outside five feet of snow. The gulf coast hard to imagine. America more violent than ever, upsetting

Please give my very warmest greeting to the Stronachs and anyone else who might care to remember me. Excuse this abbreviated note. I look forward to hearing from you. ~~Sorry not to have seen you at Pembroke prior~~ my departure.

Yours,

OLIVER

engaged cake

problems family, via

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a n s.

apology

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